

CLASSIFICATION OF THE MAIN ELEMENTS OF INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS IN MECHANICAL ENGINEERING AND THE MAIN FACTORS INFLUENCING IT

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6579128>

Safarov Sindor Sanjar O'g'li

A student of Tashkent State University of Economics
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Mashinasozlik va metallga ishlov bериш тармоғини инвестициялашда тармоқ корхоналарининг инвестицион жозибадорлиги, unga ta'sir etuvchi omillar va ularning turlari, Mashinasozlikda инвестицион жозибадорликнинг асосий унсурларини таснифланиши va investitsiyalash jarayonlari haqida so'z boradi. Shuningdek, olimlardan S.A.Jigarev va D.B.Chaginlarning ushbu yo'nalishdagi fikrlari yoritilib, tegishli fikrlar aytib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: корхоналарининг инвестицион жозибадорлиги, ularning asosiy omillari va asosiy unsurlarining tasniflanishi, investitsiyalar turlari (банк инвестициялари, асосий капиталга инвестициялар, интеллектуал инвестиция va boshqalar).

Annotation: This article discusses the investment attractiveness of enterprises in the engineering and metalworking industry, the factors influencing it and their types, the classification of the main elements of investment attractiveness in engineering and investment processes. The views of scientists S.A. Jigarev and D.B. Chagin in this direction were also highlighted.

Keywords: investment attractiveness of enterprises, classification of their main factors and key elements, types of investments (bank investments, investments in fixed assets, intellectual investments, etc.).

Аннотация В данной статье рассматривается инвестиционная привлекательность предприятий машиностроительной и металлообрабатывающей промышленности, факторы на нее влияющие и их виды, классификация основных элементов инвестиционной привлекательности в машиностроении и инвестиционные процессы. Взгляды ученых С.А. Жигарева и Д.Б. Чагин в этом направлении также выделился.

Ключевые слова: инвестиционная привлекательность предприятий, классификация их основных факторов и ключевых элементов, виды

инвестиций (банковские инвестиции, инвестиции в основной капитал, интеллектуальные инвестиции и др.).

Introduction:

With the growing demand for the engineering sector, which plays a key role in ensuring economic efficiency in all countries of the world, it is important to ensure the attractiveness of capital investments in this area, the composition of the factors influencing it and its main elements.

The main part.

The investment attractiveness of the enterprises of the industry has played an important role in investing in the engineering and metalworking industries. In this regard, a number of factors affect the investment attractiveness of enterprises, and this set of factors is conventionally divided into two groups (Table 1).

Table 1

The main factors influencing the investment attractiveness of enterprises in the engineering and metalworking industries²⁶

Internal factors	External factors
financial condition of network enterprises; efficiency of the management system; nomenclature of manufactured products; diversification of production; structure and organizational and legal form of enterprises; transparency of enterprises; transparency, reliability and completeness of reporting data.	network features; system of legislative norms; political and external economic environment; investment attractiveness of the country's regions.

It is obvious that the investment attractiveness of enterprises in the sector reflects a complete picture of the state of enterprises, and this fact serves as a basis for attracting and investing potential investors. Also, the main elements of investment attractiveness in engineering are classified as follows (Table 2).

According to S.A.Jigarev, the main goal is to modernize production in the machine-building industry and increase the efficiency of investment processes, while the following are its auxiliary goals:

- development of integration and cooperation, improvement of

²⁶ Чагин Д.В. Инвестиционная политика организаций в сфере реальных инвестиций. Экономические науки. 2013. 7 (104). - 76 с.

- economic and organizational relations;
- activation of investment processes based on scientific and technical development through logistics;
 - organization of marketing research in product sales;
 - ensuring the expansion of reproduction on the basis of modernization;
 - formation of social infrastructure and improvement of organization of labor resources use.

Table 2

Classification of key elements of investment attractiveness in engineering²⁷

№	Directions for assessing investment attractiveness	The basic structure of the elements of attractiveness
1	Production	Ensuring the growth of production of competitive products, which allows it to run an efficient business
2	Property	The formation of a management system of the property complex, which allows it to optimize social and production
3	Sale	Identify sales channels in the market for products produced in a competitive environment
4	Financial	Optimization of key financial factors, significant changes in investment processes, identification of sources of funding and assessment of its targeted use
5	Innovative	Optimization of innovative development directions, focus on increasing product competitiveness

Today, the participants in the investment process in the engineering and metalworking industry are not only investors (legal entities and individuals who invest cash and other resources), but also customers (legal entities and individuals authorized to implement investment projects), users of investment facilities (investment activities). legal entities and individuals) and investment exchanges, banks, insurance suppliers and other intermediary organizations are also participants in this process, and the

²⁷ Жигарев С.А. Формирование и развитие инвестиционных процессов в машиностроении. Автореф. диссертации на соискание ученой степени канд. экон. наук. Москва - 2010. - 22 с.

investment process includes:²⁸

- ❖ direct (real) investments in construction, repair of new productions, acquisition of means of production;
- ❖ bank investments - investment of bank resources;
- ❖ fixed capital investments - construction of new machine-building facilities and acquisition of production equipment and machinery of the relevant enterprises;
- ❖ intellectual investment - investment in the training and education of specialists and the development of scientific and technological progress;
- ❖ portfolio investments - investments in profitable shares, bonds and other securities;
- ❖ foreign investments - long-term investments in the capital of foreign owners;
- ❖ investment in human potential;
- ❖ innovative investments;
- ❖ risky investments;
- ❖ venture investment.

At present, in the world practice, the main dynamics in the trend of investing in the engineering sector in many countries is formed by the following directions²⁹:

investments in the creation of new equipment and the introduction of new developments in production based on the use of innovations and modern technologies;

investments in modernization of production (product modernization, technical and technological modernization, modernization of training and management systems);

investments in ensuring the competitiveness of the product, improving its quality and improving energy efficiency, and stimulating the production of high-tech industries, etc.

As a result, due to the above, many countries have begun to move to different ways of supporting high-tech engineering industries, and in practice, various forms of financial support for enterprises in this sector have begun to emerge.³⁰

Conclusion.

²⁸ Жигарев С.А. Теоритические аспекты развития инвестиционных процессов в машиностроении. // TERRA ECONOMICUS. Экономический вестник Ростовского государственного университета. 2009 Том 7 № 4 (часть 2). - 80 с.

²⁹ Интернет веб-сахифа маълумотлари, кириш тартиби: <http://www.globfin.ru/articles/finance/industry.htm>;
<http://www.unionexpert.ru/index.php/news/item/264>.

³⁰ Коцюбинский В.А., Комаров В.М. Перспективы развития высокотехнологического сектора России. М.:2015. - 17 с.

The analysis showed that in recent years, the demand for products of the machine-building industries with high capacity of innovation and science and technology in world markets has increased. As a result, there have been significant changes in the export structure of many countries, and the share of products of this sector in the commodity structure of exports has increased.

REFERENCES:

1. Чагин Д.В. Инвестиционная политика организаций в сфере реальных инвестиций. Экономические науки. 2013. 7 (104). - 76 с.
2. Жигарев С.А. Формирование и развитие инвестиционных процессов в машиностроении. Автореф. диссертации на соискание ученой степени канд. экон. наук. Москва - 2010. - 22 с.
3. Жигарев С.А. Теоритические аспекты развития инвестиционных процессов в машиностроении. // TERRA ECONOMICUS. Экономический вестник Ростовского государственного университета. 2009 Том 7 № 4 (часть 2). - 80 с.
4. **Khursandov K, Safarov S.** PROBLEMS OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS AND EFFICIENT USE OF INVESTMENTS IN THE FIELD OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING AND METALWORKING. Tashkent State University of Economics Journal "Economics and Education".
5. <http://www.globfin.ru/articles/finance/industry.htm>;
6. <http://www.unionexpert.ru/index.php/news/item/264>.